

THE MAIN FEATURES OF TERMINOLOGY TRANSLATION**Tairova Maxfuza Abdusattorovna**

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Annotation: The aim of the article is to reveal the main features of terminology in translation process. Terminology translation plays a crucial role in fields such as science, technology, law, and medicine, where precision and consistency are paramount. The article examines key aspects of terminology translation, including the importance of understanding both the source and target languages, the role of cultural context, and the need for adaptation to specific disciplines.

Keywords: Terminology, translation, literature, philosophy, theory.

In world linguistics, it is being crucial to pay an attention to the field of terminology translation. In recent years, modern linguistics has witnessed a significant increase in interest regarding the study of specific sublanguages that cater to various fields of professional activity. This heightened focus on languages for special purposes can largely be attributed to the dramatic proliferation of specialized terminology across diverse scientific disciplines. As a result, this surge in terminological vocabulary has begun to permeate everyday speech, extending far beyond the confines of professional communicative contexts that would typically involve expert discourse. One of the prominent characteristics of our contemporary era is that terminology, once confined to specialists, is now being integrated into general conversations by individuals who may not possess formal training in specific fields. This trend is particularly evident in technical discourse, where technical terminology is increasingly utilized in a variety of non-specialist contexts. The ongoing advancement of technology and the rapid pace of technical progress contribute to the continuous evolution of this vocabulary, necessitating a deeper understanding of its structural and semantic features.

The author of this article delves into these attributes of English terminology as it applies within technical texts. A thorough examination of how these terms are structured and their meanings is crucial for effective communication in technical and professional environments. Moreover, the article addresses the complexities involved in translating terminology in different languages, an endeavor that poses unique challenges, especially given the dynamic nature of new terminology that frequently emerges in various

fields. The analysis of terminology is grounded primarily in the examination of technical literature, which is integral to modern life and production processes. As industries grow and scientific and technological advancements continue to unfold, a substantial number of new terms are generated, many of which remain absent from established dictionaries. This swift development can create notable hurdles for translators who are faced with the task of conveying these newly coined terms into another language accurately and effectively.

Overall, this study highlights the necessity of understanding the ongoing growth and transformation of specialized vocabularies, as well as the need for linguists and translators to adapt their approaches in response to the challenges posed by this ever-evolving landscape of technical terminology.

There are a lot of concepts underlying translation theories. According to Bensoussan, some of these concepts of translation is closely related to the reading process. In addition to this, both well-known scientists Hatim and Munday (2004) suggest that translation is a process involving the negotiation of meaning between producers and receivers of the text. In terms of Larson (1984) states that in general translation communicates, as much as possible, the same meaning that was understood by the speakers of the source language, using the normal language form of the receptor language, while maintaining the dynamics of the original source-language text. She also expresses that the goal of a translator should o produce a receptor language text (a translation) that is idiomatic; i.e., one that has the same meaning as the source-language text, but is expressed in the natural form of the receptor language.

Before delving into the complexities of term translation issues within scientific and technical texts, it is essential to first explore the definition and linguistic characteristics of what constitutes a term. According to the linguist O.S. Akhmanova, a term can be understood as a specific word or a combination of words within a particular language that has been deliberately created, accepted, borrowed, or otherwise adopted for the precise expression of specialized notions and for denoting specific objects or concepts. This perspective highlights the intentional nature of term creation in linguistic contexts, indicating that terms are not arbitrary but rather serve a distinct purpose in facilitating clear communication about specialized subjects. Similarly, S.V. Grinev offers a comparable definition, asserting that a term is a unique lexical unit whether a single word or a phrase that is characteristic of a particular language and is employed to provide an exact name for a specific concept. This definition emphasizes the importance of specificity and clarity in the use of terms, as they

must accurately convey the intended meaning within their given context. Both definitions underscore a crucial aspect of terminology: that terms must be unambiguously identified and understood within their respective contexts. This necessity for clarity is particularly significant in scientific and technical domains, where any ambiguity could lead to misunderstanding or miscommunication. Therefore, a thorough understanding of the linguistic nature of terms is vital before undertaking the study of their translation issues.

According to the outlined requirements, it is essential to distinguish between two primary categories of terms used within scientific and technical contexts:

1) general scientific and technical terms, and 2) specific nomenclature terms. The first category, which encompasses general scientific and technical terms, is designed to represent broad concepts and principles that are widely applicable across various fields of science and technology. These terms help facilitate communication and understanding among professionals and laypersons alike, as they encompass ideas that are foundational to numerous disciplines. On the other hand, the second category consists of specific terms that are part of specialized nomenclature within particular scientific or technical fields. These terms are crucial for precise communication within a given discipline, as they denote particular concepts and phenomena that may not be recognized outside of that professional context. T.M. Dementieva explains that terminology, which comprises a coherent set of terms, functions as an autonomous component of any national language. This terminology is deeply intertwined with professional practices and activities, reflecting the specific knowledge and expertise required in various scientific and technical professions. In any branch of science, technology, or production, terms are systematically categorized into their own unique systems. These systems establish conceptual relationships with the knowledge specific to a profession, effectively harnessing the power of language to express these intricate connections. It is noteworthy that, in general language use outside the boundaries of established terminology a word may possess multiple meanings or interpretations. However, when a term is integrated into a defined terminology, it undergoes a transformation that bestows it with a level of unambiguity. This shift ensures that the term conveys a single, clear meaning that is universally understood within the context of that specific field, thereby enhancing clarity and reducing the potential for miscommunication.

The primary challenge in achieving translation equivalence within scientific and technical texts lies in accurately reproducing the original content

while utilizing the terminological framework of the target language. The disparities in the terminological systems between the source and target languages present significant obstacles in the translation process of these texts. Consequently, it is essential to examine the terminological systems and explore methods for translating partially equivalent and non-equivalent vocabulary. The investigation of terminology represents a critical aspect of the study of scientific and technical texts. A term or phrase is indicative of a concept specific to a particular field of knowledge or activity. Identifying the differences in the conceptual systems represented by the terms from both the source and target languages is a vital step toward achieving interlanguage harmonization of term systems, ultimately facilitating effective translation of terms in their respective fields of application.

In conclusion, the translation of terminology plays a vital role in facilitating effective communication within specialized fields, as it ensures the accurate conveyance of knowledge across diverse languages and cultures. The primary characteristics of terminology translation encompass a deep understanding of the subtleties inherent in both the source and target languages, along with the technical or scientific context in which the terminology is utilized. Significant challenges include addressing language-specific concepts, ensuring consistency, and modifying terms to align with the cultural and linguistic standards of the intended audience. Various translation techniques such as direct translation, borrowing, calques, and neologisms are employed to maintain meaning and enhance clarity. Successful terminology translation not only bridges linguistic divides but also improves comprehension in sectors such as law, science, technology, and medicine, thereby contributing to the global exchange of knowledge and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. Ultimately, the precision and adaptability of terminology translation are essential for promoting effective communication in an increasingly interconnected world.

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